

seasons. Spikelet fertility for each plant was evaluated visually. Varieties showing more than 80% spikelet fertility were classified as restorers, those showing 10-79% fertility as partial restorers, and those with less OM88 and IR28228-12-3-1-3 were suspected maintainers for IR46830A and IR54752A, respectively.

The effectivity of maintainers will be confirmed by backcrossing and scoring individual plants of BC progenies for pollen sterility. Completely pollen sterile BC progenies would indicate that the suspected maintainer is effective, and could be converted that into a CMS line. □

Restorers and maintainers for male sterile lines identified at CLRRRI, Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam, 1987-89 dry and wet seasons.

Male sterile line	Fertility restorer lines	Partial restorer lines	Suspected maintainer lines
IR46829A	NN3A, NN4B	IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	OM88
IR46830A	NN3A, OM576 IR66, IR29723-143-3-2-2-1	OM86-9, ITA212 IR64,OM80 IR28228-12-3-1-1-2	OM88
IR48483A	OM86-9, OM90, IR54 IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 IR31801-124-1-3	NN7A IR28228-12-3-1-1-2	IR31917-45-3-2-2
IR54752A	IR64, OM80, OM576 NN4B, NN5B, IR54 IR29723-143-3-2-1	ITA212 IR27316-60-3-2-2	IR28228-12-3-1-1-2

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Breeding methods—tissue culture

D₂₀₂₆, a promising rice dwarf mutant of Guangluai 4

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We irradiated seeds of Guangluai 4, a short-duration local rice variety with high yield and wide adaptability, with ⁶⁰Co r-rays (30 kR) + Ar⁺Laser (80 J/cm²).

Starting with the M₂, plants were selected for dwarf stature. Mutant D₂₀₂₆, selected in the M₄, has significantly shorter plants, shorter panicles, and lower 1,000-grain weight than Guangluai 4 (see table). But it has higher seed-setting.

The mutant has a good plant type with plant height of 46.2-58.4 cm. It should be a good source of the dwarf character in breeding projects. □

Agronomic characters of the dwarf mutant D₂₀₂₆ and its mother variety Guangluai 4. Hunan, China, 1988.

Characteristic	Mutant D ₂₀₂₆	Guangluai 4
Plant height (cm)	52.3	74.3
Panicle length (cm)	15.2	19.6
Seed-setting rate (%)	85.9	81.8
1,000-grain weight (g)	17.9	23.8
Yield per plant (g)	8.3	16.4

Decline of morphogenic potential in microspore-derived calli from indica/japonica and japonica/japonica F₁ hybrids

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In large-scale anther culture plant production, the callus transfer activity consumes time, medium, and space.

Hence, it is more efficient to concentrate on cultures possessing good morphogenic potential.

Rice anthers inoculated onto a semisolid induction medium produce visible microspore-derived calli from 4 to 10 wk after inoculation, in an asynchronous callus induction process. Transferring calli to the regeneration medium when they are 1-2 mm in size ensures better regeneration efficiency. But that requires repeated callus transfers.

Green plant regenerating ability (GPRA) of microspore-derived calli as a function of time when calli attained transferable stage, IRRI. 1989. Each liter of the callus-inducing medium (N6AK) = N6 basal salts, Fe source, and vitamins supplemented with 2 mg naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), 0.5 mg kinetin, 60 g sucrose, and 5.5 g agarose; each liter of the regeneration medium (R6) = N6 basal salts, Fe source, and vitamins supplemented with 1 mg kinetin and 0.1 mg naphthalene acetic acid, 40 g sucrose, and 5.5 g agarose.

The production of calli and their regenerating ability are known to decline with increasing age of anther culture. This is perhaps due to a depletion of available nutrients in the unrenewed culture medium or to a release of toxic compounds from the senescent anther walls, or to both.

To assess the time beyond which callus transfers are no longer profitable, we monitored the green plant-regenerating ability (GPRA) of calli arising between 4 and 8 wk after anther inoculation of four rice F₁ hybrids (see figure).

GPRA of aus/japonica hybrid Kele/IRAT216 and indica/japonica hybrids IR64/Azucena and IR64/IRAT216 calli increased slightly to week 6 of culture, then decreased (see table). The morphogenic ability of calli that attained the transferable stage 8 wk after anther plating remained at an acceptable level in Kele/IRAT216 and IR64/Azucena. However, the callus GPRA of IRAT216/Azucena, which decreased dramatically as early as week 5 of culture, was reduced to only 10% in week 8.

These results suggest that it is still worthwhile to transfer late-emerging calli in indica/japonica anther cultures, up to 2 mo after plating. However, only early microspore calli had a satisfactory GPRA in the japonica/japonica hybrid.

Such differential retentions of GPRA among the hybrids investigated may correspond to the histological differences in the calli. That merits further investigation. □

Green plant regeneration in microspore-derived calli of F₁ hybrids as a function of aging in anther culture.^a IRRI, 1989.

	Anthen			4 wk			5 wk			6 wk			7 wk			8 wk			Total		
	Inoculated (no.)	Callusing (no.)	%	S	R	%	S	R	%	S	R	%	S	R	%	S	R	%	S	R	%
IR64/Azucena	23,905	6,466	27.2	1,523	142	9.3	1,031	106	10.3	995	110	11	762	81	10.6	483	32	6.6	4,794	471	9.8
IR64/IRAT216	17,560	3,837	21.8	675	33	4.8	714	40	5.6	659	64	9.7	341	29	8.5	212	16	7.5	2,601	182	7
Kele/IRAT216	9,700	2,872	29.8	661	27	4.1	1,015	45	4.4	783	46	5.8	711	41	5.7	138	2	1.4	3,308	161	4.9
IRAT216/Azucena	2,523	1,222	48.4	235	25	10.6	302	85	7.6	279	10	3.6	185	5	8.7	165	2	1.2	1,166	67	5.7
Total or average	53,588	14,397	(26.9)	3,094	227	7.3	3,062	216	7	2,716	230	8.5	1,999	156	7.8	998	52	5.2	11,869	881	7.4

^aS = no. of calli subcultured onto regeneration medium, R = no. of green plant-regenerating calli.

Yield potential

Stability for grain yield and its physiological attributes in rice genotypes

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Low solar radiation has been the major constraint to higher productivity of rice during the wet season (WS). A decrease of 40-60% in light intensity leads to poor productivity. Rice yield also is governed by the interaction of genetic makeup and physiological characters. Both climate and plant physiology affect the stability of rice productivity.

We studied the relative stability for grain yield over three planting seasons of six medium-duration genotypes. Seedlings (26 d old) were transplanted 6 Feb 1987, 7 Jul 1988, and 23 Oct 1987.

The statistical constants of the mean, regression coefficient (bi), and standard deviation from regression (S^{-d}i) for three parameters are given in the table. Four genotypes—Ponni, TNAU80030, CO 43, and Bhavani—registered higher photosynthetic rates than the pooled mean, but they had varied responses to changes in the environment and stability. CO 44 and IR20 were unstable for total biomass (significant values for bi and S^{-d}i).

Ponni, TNAU80030, and CO 43 registered yields higher than the pooled mean. Nonsignificant values for bi and S^{-d}i indicated the absence of a genotype x environment interaction. The three varieties appear to be widely adapted across environments and performed well even under the low-light stress environments of the wet season (Jul and Oct) plantings. □

Estimation of stability parameters for three characters in rice. Coimbatore, India.

Genotype	Photosynthetic rate at flowering (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)			Total biomass (g/m ²)			Grain yield (g/m ²)		
	Mean	bi	S ^{-d} i	Mean	bi	S ^{-d} i	Mean	bi	S ^{-d} i
Ponni	26.7	1.10*	-0.5	1175.8	0.86	-191.1	541.0	0.69	32.9
TNAU80030	26.0	0.67	-0.5	1164.0	0.79	-159.4	544.0	0.87	7.9
CO 43	25.8	1.01*	-0.5	1145.2	0.75	-145.8	550.8	0.74	75.0
CO 44	19.2	1.44**	-0.5	920.4	1.34**	1239.1**	440.0	1.26**	47.9*
Bhavani	25.8	1.21**	-0.4	999.6	1.25**	511.8*	465.3	1.31**	37.5*
IR20	22.5	0.56	-0.5	969.4	1.17	-68.3	471.0	1.71**	17.2
Pooled mean	24.3	1.00	-	1062.4	1.00	-	502.7	1.00	-
SE	1.3	0.99	-	70.8	0.23	-	35.6	0.39	-